

Guidance and Counselling Services and Administration of Public Junior Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined guidance and counselling services and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and tested for this study. The correlation research design was adopted for this study. The study was carried out in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The population of this study was 2,665 respondents which comprised 48 principals and 2617 junior secondary school teachers from 48 junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The sample size adopted for this study was 390 which comprised 360 teachers and 30 school principals in junior secondary schools in Rivers State. Self-designed questionnaire was used to gather the responses of the respondents in this study. A questionnaire titled “Guidance and Counselling Services and Administration of Junior Secondary Schools was used for collection of data in the study. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts. Cronbach Alpha Reliability formula which gave a reliability index of 0.80, 0.77, 0.79, 0.81, and 0.82 was used. Pearson Product Moment Correlations. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to provide answer to the research questions while t-transformation formula was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that there is a significant relationship between guidance and counselling services rendered by school counsellors’ and administration of junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. It was recommended that professional counsellors should be employed in junior secondary schools so as to encourage orientation services that could enhance effective administration.

Keywords: Guidance, Counselling Services, Administration, Public, Junior Secondary, School.

INTRODUCTION

Guidance and Counselling is a professional field which has a broad range of activities and services aimed at assisting individuals to understand themselves, others, school environment and attain abilities to adjust accordingly (Eremie & Jackson, 2019). Counselling is a process of helping the individual towards overcoming obstacles to his/her personal growth which could be educational, societal, or personal, wherever it may be encountered. In this regard, the undergraduates strive to achieve optimum development of his personal resources. This is expected to be curbed through orientation services. First among other services is the orientation service. Orientation of counselling services is essentially for all newly students, all newly posted lecturers and non-academic staff of the school (Anagbogu, 2016). The services are supposed to be provided by the institutional guidance counsellor immediately the new undergraduates resumes, newly posted teachers and students arrives the school on

admission/appointment. It is not a one-day affair. It may take the first two to three days immediately after they have entered the school. According to Gunkle (1955) posits that it is essential to guidance counsellors furnish new students with vital information that guides their behaviours and enhance their environmental adjustment to the school. This role will not only improve students' conduct in the school but also enhance the effectiveness of administrative policies guiding students' conduct in the school environment.

School counsellors in secondary schools play a crucial role in providing career orientation services to students to help them navigate the challenges of the work environment and prevent career disorientation (Dislere & Vronska, 2021). It is essential for school administrators to support guidance and counselling (G/C) activities by allocating adequate funding, providing necessary equipment and infrastructure, ensuring sufficient time for counsellors and students, and promoting continuous staff training and development programs (Oguzie, 2014). Novice school counsellors prioritize building relationships with school administrators and teachers to ensure effective functioning of counselling services (Atli, 2020). In the context of secondary schools, counsellors are increasingly offering wellbeing support to students, with a growing emphasis on professional services and the presence of school counsellors in Australian secondary schools (Bignold & Anderson, 2023).

The roles of school counsellors encompass a wide range of tasks including behaviour management, psychological assessment, program development, consultation, and individual and group counselling (Barletta, 1996). Collaboration between school counsellors, teachers, and school administrators has been shown to lead to better outcomes in supporting students compared to counsellors working independently (Sadana & Kumar, 2021).

School administration encompasses a wide range of responsibilities crucial for the effective functioning of educational institutions. It involves overseeing various aspects such as student enrollment, financial management, resource allocation, and human resource management (David et al., 2019). School administrators are pivotal in creating a conducive and inclusive learning environment for diverse student populations (Minkos, Sassu, Patwa, Theodore & Femc-Bagwell, 2017). They are also increasingly being recognized as technology leaders responsible for integrating technology into education (Aktaş & Karaca, 2022). Effective school administration involves not only managing operational tasks but also fostering a vision for the school, promoting innovation, and being proactive in school improvement efforts (Apriani, 2023).

Orientation as a counselling service is provided to an individual or a group of individuals who are just entering a new environment. The individual may be a student who has just started schooling (in the primary, secondary or tertiary institutions). If not well groomed by a school counsellor the student life will likely be crowded with obnoxious behaviours (Onyekpa, 2021). Curtailing students' indiscipline is a significant aspect of school administration that requires a rigid administrative policy. These policies are to be effectively communicated to the students so as to enhance their behavioural expression within the school (Matt, 2022). Hence, this require orientation programme of the guidance and counsellors to communicate school disciplinary polices to students.

Guidance services carried out by the school guidance counsellor are made up of the execution of a number of highly specialized services that constitutes the pattern of activities within the school guidance programme. Follow up service is an essential aspect of the counselling programs offered by school counsellors. In this service, counsellor follow up students who have been initially exposed to counselling therapy to determine the effectiveness of the programme. Ijale, Fakokunde and Aminu (2022) defined follow-up service is a continuous monitoring programme designed to evaluate the intervention procedures in relation to client's progress and adjustment. This service is undertaken as systematic evaluation of whether the guidance services in particular and the educational programme in general have satisfied the needs of the clients. According to Malunfashi (2014), follow-up service refers to the formal and systematic monitoring of the individual progress of current clients who have undergone academic advising, counselling, referral, placement, or any special intervention programme. Follow-up service is an integral parts of guidance services. It is concerned with what happened to clients after they have been

counseled. Follow-up services enable the guidance counsellor to see through the services he/she must have offered the counsellee. It is an avenue through which the counsellor determines the effectiveness of planning and placement activities (Sokan & Osarenren, 2005).

His service allows the counsellor to see and verify whether the guided or counseled individual or group is coping after guidance or counselling. The primary aim of the follow up services rendered by school counsellors are to ascertain the progress of a students. By ascertaining the progress of a student, the feedback obtained are likely to be implemented in the adjustment of school administration. Secondly, follow up service gain data which may identify weakness in the various phases of the counselling and school administration policies leading to students' low progress in behavioral adjustment. Moreover, follow up services by counsellors can also help evaluate the effectiveness of the placement activities and obtain opinions concerning the need for modification in the life of the experiences of former clients (Ijale et al. 2022).

Guidance and counselling are a crucial tool in the educational line for guiding children away from the harmful notions in a child induced by his/her peers or environment to a positive perspective (Lasisi & Ibraheem, 2023). Hence, every school needs a guidance counsellor to help modify the children's future through counselling therapy. The tenacity for guidance and counselling in schools is to improve students' academic performance, adoptive positive study attitudes and habits, increase acquisitions and application of required resolution skills and lessening school failures. Students and teachers in secondary schools have different perceptions towards guidance and counselling services. These perceptions determine whether they seek for the guidance and counselling services or not. The perceptions also affect their behaviour, academic performance and everyday experiences. The increase of indiscipline and social ills in secondary schools in Nigeria such as disrespecting teachers, misunderstandings with parents, drug and substance abuse, strikes, teenage pregnancies, not to mention the poor performance in the national examinations, are indications that either there are guidance and counselling services or the students are not encouraged to seek for such services even if available.

As individuals develop through stages of life and educational attainment, they encounter problems, challenges and conflict situations. These individuals also need to develop value systems, make decisions, set goals and work towards them. All these cannot be achieved without self-understanding and decision-making skills which are not innate but needs to be developed. The need to address these challenges and to promote educational success and healthy life requires the attention of guidance and counselling programs by individuals or students. Guidance and counselling is a term usually used together which focus on assisting individual attain self-understanding and direction, although attempts have been made by various authors to define the term separately.

Guidance and counselling are the assistance made available by qualified and trained persons to an individual of any age to help him/her to manage his/her own life activities, develop his/her own points of view, make his/her own decisions and carry his/her own burden. Counselling as a process of utilizing professional skills by a person (counsellor) to assist another (client) in a person-to-person relationship to achieve the resolution of general life problems, in order to attain proper development and functioning. General life problems here, refers to all aspects of the individual's life which includes; personal, social, educational and vocational among others, as no single individual is said to be free from trouble or problem. Guidance and counselling is therefore designed to help individuals/students in their different problems and concerns, so that they grow up well-adjusted individuals capable not only of living productive lives but are also prepared to contribute their quota to the development of their society.

In the light of the above, guidance counselling aids students align with the demands of the school system as designed by the school administrators. The maladjustment of students to school systems can create a distorted school administration and lead to unsuccessful administration system. To create a worthwhile environment whereby students, teachers and administrators thrive in a structured environment is where guidance and counsellors comes in. Guidance and counselling services equips students to undertake increasing responsibilities for their decisions and grow in their ability to understand and accept the results

of their choices. The focus of Guidance and counselling in schools is to address the needs and concerns of students or learners at different levels of academic or educational development.

The primary mission of a school's guidance and counselling program is to provide a broad spectrum of personnel services to the students. Denga in Onyekpa (2021) referred to these services as "clusters of formalized educational services designed by the school to assist students to achieve self-knowledge or self-understanding which is necessary for them to attain the fullest self-development and self-realization of their potentials". These services include: student appraisal service, information service, counselling service, placement service, orientation service, referral service, follow-up and evaluation service and research service. In accordance to the statement above, counsellor educators see guidance as a comprehensive and developmental programme designed to benefit all students in their journey through school. The counsellor is there to design and address the developmental needs of students appropriate to their age group. In that light the function of a guidance counsellor is not easily defined. Mime (2010) suggested that the function definition was dependent upon the group of people creating the definition. For example, students may see the function of guidance counsellors much more different than other teachers. In turn, teachers may perceive the function of counsellors much differently than administrators, who may view their function much differently that the counsellors themselves. Other variables come into place when trying to determine the role of school counsellors, for example, the role a counsellor performs at the high school level may differ greatly from the role of an elementary counsellor.

Guidance and Counselling is a newcomer in the Nigerian educational system, hence the counsellor and his services are strange to many but the teacher has been a major factor, therefore the perception of teachers has a direct impact on the guidance and counselling services in our schools (Eremie & Bob-Manuel, 2020). Some teachers see the guidance counsellors as fellow colleagues, so they should teach like other teachers in the school.

Most teachers think that the role of guidance counsellors is contradicting to teaching and is auxiliary to administrative functions of the school. Teachers perceive the counsellor as a helper who impacts positively to the overall development of the school programmes. And some believe that counsellor do not have any function in the schools. The misunderstanding or confusion of the roles between the teachers and the guidance counsellor has created different teachers' perceptions of counsellors' roles in the schools, especially public schools.

Statement of the Problem

The school system cannot be complete without the presence of counselors in our schools. The awaking of the Guidance and counseling services in our society is on the low side. The awareness of Guidance and counseling has not really taken root in the society. This is because the roles and meaning of Guidance and counseling services has not been understood by the society, especially the teachers who mostly work alongside counselors. The researcher has observed that there appears to be suspicion between the counsellors and teachers which has created underlying educational problems such as being a confidant to students in school; an academic helper, guidance to student in career choice career exploration and planning for students after graduation just to mention a few for the counsellors. As a result, the attitude of teachers towards guidance and counselling has been negative.

One of the main problems of the effective Guidance and Counselling profession in Nigeria is the ignorance of the real aim or target of the counselling job by most Nigerian counsellors, the public, parents, teachers, principals and students. Recently, teachers' perceptions of counsellor's role created contradicting motives in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The ignorance of the role of the counselor has negative effect on individuals especially the adolescences in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The researchers also observed that the efforts of a genuinely active counsellor to organize and administer a guidance programme are at times wanted by the un-co-operative attitude of the school principal. The fact that some school principals and teachers are not quite happy to see guidance counsellors posted to their schools. Teachers feel jealous of counsellors as a result do not often refer problem students to them.

School administrators on the other hand appear not to be in agreement with professional counsellors with regards to their roles and functions. It has been carefully observed that principals in schools have not recognized guidance counsellors as a useful component in ensuring effective administration. They mostly assume that school activities could be smoothly carried out without the presence of the school counsellor. This perception has most times resulted in increase in low academic performance, low student-teacher relationship, disrupted academic policies amongst others. The problem that prompted this study was that the display of certain antisocial behaviours among teenagers in schools which make the school administration look poor and ineffective. The question arising is that does relationship exists between guidance and counselling services and school administration? To provide establish this, the researcher sought to investigate guidance and counselling services and school administration in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between guidance and counselling services and administration of junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The study is meant to achieve the following objectives:

1. Investigate the relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.
2. Examine the relationship between school counsellors' follow-up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The researcher developed the following research questions to guide the conduct of the study:

1. What is the relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?
2. What is the relationship between counsellors' follow-up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The researcher formulated the following hypotheses to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis
2. There is no significant relationship between follow-up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The design used for the study was a correlation research design. The study was conducted in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Rivers State is one of the thirty-six (36) states in Nigeria.

The population of this study was 2,665 respondents which comprised of 48 principals and 2617 junior secondary school teachers from 48 public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The sample size adopted for this study was 390 which comprised of 360 teachers and 30 school principals in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. Taro Yamene formula was applied to obtain a sample size of 346 in the population of teachers, however to obtain a favorable sample size the researcher used 360 as the sample size. Two self-designed questionnaires were used to gather the responses of the respondents in this study.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis between Students' Orientation and Administration of Public Junior Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

Variables	N	$\sum X \sum Y$	$\sum X^2 \sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal	R/ship
Students' Orientation Service (X)	320	2823	6790			
				83110	+0.69	Strong
School Administration (Y)	320	3210	8704			

Table1: presents the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. The result showed that the r-calculated value was +0.69, indicating a strong positive relationship. The result implies that there is a relationship between the orientation services rendered by counsellors to students and effective administration of junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. The r-cal value (+0.69) obtained infers that when orientation service organized for students it becomes easier to achieve the objectives of school administration especially in public schools.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between follow-up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis between Follow up Service and Administration of Public Junior Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

Variables	N	$\sum X \sum Y$	$\sum X^2 \sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal	R/ship
Follow up Service (X)	320	2093	6124			
				81082	+0.71	Strong
School Administration (Y)	320	3210	8704			

Table 4.2 displays the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis between follow up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. The analysis output showed that the r-calculated value was +0.71, indicating a strong positive relationship. The implication of the analysis output was that the more counsellors' follow up service is provided to students it could help to enhance and improve administrative strategies of principals in junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 3: t-Transformation Result on the Significant Relationship between Student Orientation Service and Administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-cal	t-crit.	α	Decision
Students' Orientation service	320						
		318	+0.69	17.06	± 1.96	0.05	Rejected
School Administration	320						

Table 3 above revealed the summary of t-transformation analysis on the relationship between students' orientation service and administration of junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers

State. The result showed that the t-transformation value was 17.06 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 318 degrees of freedom. Since the t-trans value is greater than the t-crit, and the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis was hence rejected. This shows that there is a significant relationship between students' orientation service rendered by guidance counsellors and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between follow-up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

Table 4. t-Transformation Result on the Significant Relationship between Follow Up Service and Administration of Junior Secondary Schools

Variables	N	Df	r-value	t-cal	t-crit.	α	Decision
Follow-up service	320						
		318	+0.71	21.47	± 1.96	0.05	Rejected
School Administration	320						

Table. above displayed the summary of t-transformation analysis on the relationship between follow up service and administration of junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The analysis output revealed that the t-transformation value was 17.06 which was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 318 degrees of freedom. Since the t-trans value (21.47) is greater than the t-crit, and the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis was hence rejected. This shows that there is a significant relationship between students' follow up service rendered by guidance counsellors and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis

Summary of Major Findings

The major findings in this are as follows

1. Research question one shows that there is a strong positive relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. The tested null hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.
2. Research questions two revealed that there is also a strong positive correlation between follow up service and administration of public junior secondary school. The result of the null hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance revealed that there is a significant relationship between follow-up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Firstly, findings on research question one as revealed in table one showed that there is a strong positive ($r = +0.69$) relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. The tested null hypothesis presented in table 4.5 revealed that there is a significant ($p\text{-value}=0.000 > \alpha=0.05$) relationship between students' orientation service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. This finding is closely related to the findings of Onyekpa (2021) who did a study on the utilization of orientation service for handling problem behaviours of undergraduates in public universities in South East, Nigeria found that orientation service is essential in school administration with respect to both teachers and students. The author further observed that administrators need orientation services carefully carried out by school counsellors for effective implementation and functioning of administrative policies in the school. In the same vein, Eremie and Jackson (2019) added that orientation service is a crucial programme that aids

administrators in ensuring that new students are accustomed with the administrative structures and demands of the school. Still supporting the findings Atsuwe and Achebulu in Onyekpa (2021) observed in their study that guidance and counselling services have great influences on students' academic performance in secondary school.

Secondly, the findings of research questions two as presented in table 4.2 showed that there is also a strong positive correlation between counsellors follow up service and administration of public junior secondary school. The result of the null hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance in table 4.6 revealed that there is a significant ($p\text{-value}=0.000 < \alpha=0.05$) relationship between counsellors' follow-up service and administration of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The finding is in alignment with Ijale et al., (2022) who stated that follow up services by counsellors can also help evaluate the effectiveness of the placement activities and obtain opinions concerning the need for modification in the life of the experiences of former clients leading to effective school administration. Also, Lasisi and Ibraheem (2023) provided in their study, that guidance and counselling are a crucial tool in the educational line for guiding children away from the harmful notions in a child induced by his/her peers or environment to a positive perspective which stands as the achievement of general objective of education.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between guidance and counselling services rendered by school counsellors' and administration of public junior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. This means that when school counselors effectively discharge their guidance and counselling duties, it would help to alleviate school administrative issues and burden. Thereby leading to an effective discharge of school administrative measures in junior secondary school. The service of guidance and counselling is not underrated even in the administration of secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made

1. Professional counsellors should be employed in junior secondary schools so as to encourage orientation services that could enhance effective administration
2. Counselors should be trained to effectively carried out professional appraisal and follow up services that administrators could use to re-adjust their administrative strategies and obtain educational goals and objectives

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